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“BEYOND ORDINARY WITH THE RHYTHM OF EXTRAORDINARY FAMILY”

Every person around the globe has their own unique rhythm in life. Some people move fast beating deadlines and scheduled meetings. Some move slowly at their own pace feeling every beat of the moment. As each of us move at our own rhythm, every family does, too. Some families are filled with day-to-day busy schedules, fast and loud with alarm clocks waking them up for hurried mornings. Others pass softly, like a beautiful melody played on a piano in the lobby of a five-star hotel. But our family is extraordinary. We learned a diverse rhythm the day a beautiful human being came out in this world. He is Liam, my younger brother. He was born a little early than full term, so tiny weighing less than one kilogram and diagnosed with Down Syndrome.

When my mom came to her senses few hours after her delivery to Liam via cesarean section, the pediatrician spoke in very clear voice, giving over a brochure to my parents loaded with unfamiliar medical terms. He explained my brother's condition. At that moment, hope came late as fear and uncertainty rushed first inside the private room of the hospital where my parents stayed. My mom carefully listening to the doctor, though speechless but crying the whole time, while my father was in shock. My younger brother was staying at the neonatal intensive care unit with oxygen unit attached to him as he was having difficulty in breathing. A lot of questions freely filled in the air. Would Liam live independently in the future? Would he learn the alphabet? Would he speak the words dad and mom and sister? Would he walk, run and ride a bike?

But Liam, even as a baby, had an eccentric gift for altering the mood of any room or place. He smiled every so often—mouth open wide, fearless, infectious smiles that seemed too huge for his so cute and tiny face. It will always be a smile as if he knew something we did not comprehend yet. I know life would not become easier, but every time I see that smile, I know life would become richer for sure. As my brother continues to grow, though slowly, we ensure he come with us everywhere we go. Every time people look at him differently, more often with cruelty and meanness, my heart breaks repeatedly. How can these people do that to such an innocent and adorable baby like Liam? That question always lingers in my mind as my heart shutters in pain.

Through time, challenges visited our family quietly but very often. I have witnessed how hard my parents cry every night until they fall asleep. I can't help but also cry and pray for better days to come. Appointments in therapy sessions swapped our regular weekends. My mom practiced exercises to strengthen Liam's muscles before she practiced how to rest her body again. My dad, on the other hand, took extra hustle for work since bills for household utilities and Liam's expenses piled up like bundle of papers. Sometimes fatigue and exhaustion, even uninvited, will take a seat on our dinner table and cannot be ignored- just impossible!

There came another battleground- it's school. When Liam started attending classes under special education program, some people he passes around will stare at him as if he were different in the bad way. Others looks at him from head to foot as if he doesn't belong in that place. Some avoided him completely. I will never forget one afternoon when he came home strangely quiet. He dropped off his backpack and lunch bag on the floor, and he whispered, "They shouted and laughed at me when I talk." Then, Liam cried out loud as if he suffered from a bleeding wound. My mom hugged him tightly while fighting back tears of her own. It made me realized that in moments like that, people can be judgmental in just one snap. Our family eventually discovered that the most difficult challenge we face was not actually Down syndrome per se, but the unkindness, disrespect and cruelty of the world around to persons with disability like Liam.

Nevertheless, there were small victories in between the difficult times in our family life that others might never notice. The first time Liam closed the button of his uniform, my dad applauded and cheered out loud like his basketball team had won a championship after a decade. When he learned to write his full name without any assistance, we secured the paper with a magnet to the refrigerator and hang it there as though it was a great masterpiece of all time. Even simple talks and conversations with Liam became celebrations. Every new term or word he verbalized clearly felt like opening a box of treasured gift.

One sunny morning, Liam insisted on helping mom cook breakfast since its weekend. He assisted her in making pancakes. The kitchen became a tragedy just like ground zero—flour on the counter, eggshells mixed with egg in the bowl, butter somehow on the wall, and water with oil around the table. Our voices filled the kitchen as we laughed out loud until our stomachs ache. The pancakes were bumpy and somewhat burned, but Liam proudly announced that it is "restaurant quality." Tears continuously fell from our eyes uncontrolled as happiness overflowed our hearts. We tastefully ate every bite of the pancakes especially prepared and cooked by my dear brother. That moment is truly one for the books!

These circumstances were such tiny wins that carried vast significance because they were earned with persistence, determination, and most of all, love. Families like ours learn to quantify success in a different manner. We do not count merely on certificates of recognition, plaques, salaries, or prizes. We count bravery and courage. We rejoice resilience and problems resolved. We treasure every single moment most people rush past. We enjoy life one day at a time.

Over the years, Liam changed all of us in ways no one really expected. My mom became more empathetic and compassionate towards struggling parents especially those having a family member with special needs. My dad, once tame and held in reserve, learned to speak up affection and warmth openly. I became less ashamed and self-conscious by differences and more mindful of invisible battles people around me carry every day. Most importantly, Liam taught us that human worth is not measured by speed, achievement or perfection, not even intelligence. As a culture, society often adores and look up to those who people who move fastest, speak smartest, or accomplish the most. But Liam is extraordinary as he moves at his own pace. Yet he notices the secluded classmate whom no one talks to. He always remembers birthdays without giving him reminders. He openly hugs people as if he is healing them from pain they are going through. He smiles at them with his eyes saying that everything is fine and life is worth living.

In our family, there are still difficult and challenging situations. I guess we can never get away with it though. The future and forthcoming days may remain uncertain. My parents still apprehended about who will take care of Liam when they grow old. Sometimes frustration knocks the door and visits our home readily. Sometimes fear does too. But our unconditional love for one another has become stronger than both. It

overruled everything that bothers us. We continue to hold on the fact that as long as we love each other, life will be easy and happy.

A family like us, with a member with down syndrome is nothing ordinary. Our story is not just a reminder of constant inspiration, life struggles, gloominess or endless sadness. It is something even more- it is real. It is missed weekend hang-outs or parties, missed bus rides, discriminations every now and then, therapy sessions, sleepless nights due to fear of uncertainty, chaos at home, tears everywhere even in parking lots, unforgettable laughter during burnt pancake breakfasts and a lot more. It is learning persistence, tolerance and acceptance one slow step at a time. It is realizing that “normal” or “ordinary” was never the goal to begin with. But rather, to live an extraordinary life in ordinary ways.

Perhaps, to live normally just like any other family is way far more with us. But one thing is for sure, our family is beyond ordinary. We have many victories though small; we celebrate it even more. It may not be considered vast achievement but probably our greatest small win is that we stopped trying to become a perfect one and became a family grounded with genuinely human connection instead. Given a chance to reset my life from the start, I will still choose them and I will always choose them over and over again.

